

Synthesis of some New Pyrazolin-5-ones

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Synthesis of some sulfonamoylhydrazonopyrazolin-5-ones have been reported.

Keeping in view the biological importance of hydrazono group and pyrazolin-5-ones¹, some substituted arylhydrazono derivatives of pyrazolin-5-ones have been synthesized.

The sulfonamoylpyrazolin-5-ones (**2**) have been synthesized by reacting the ethyl acetoacetate derivative (**1**) with 4-nitrophenylhydrazine (Scheme 1) in good yields.

Scheme 1. Reagents : (i) NaNO_2 ; conc. HCl, (ii) $\text{CH}_3\text{COCH}_2\text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5$, NaOAc; (iii) CH_3COOH , $p\text{-O}_2\text{NC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NHNH}_2$.

Experimental

M.ps. are uncorrected.

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 883 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra on a Varian spectrophotometer (270 MHz) using tetramethylsilane as internal standard. M.ps. are uncorrected. Compounds were routinely checked for their purity on silica gel G plates.

Compound 1 : To sulphanilamide (0.01 mol) dissolved in a mixture of concentrated HCl (4.0 ml) and water (5.0 ml) and cooled to 0° , was added a cold aqueous solution of sodium nitrite. The diazonium salt so formed was filtered in ethanolic solution of sodium acetate (6.0 g) and ethyl acetate (0.01 mol) maintaining the temperature below 5° . The resulting yellow solid was washed with water and crystallized from ethanol to furnish **1a** (61%), m.p. 123° (Found : C, 45.98; H, 4.75; N, 13.39. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_5\text{N}_3\text{S}$ calcd. for : C, 46.00; H, 4.79; N, 13.41%); ν_{max} 3240 (NH), 3310 (NH_2), 1680 (CO, involved in hydrogen bonding), 1120 (SO_2) and 750 cm^{-1} (p -disubstituted phenyl); δ (CDCl_3) 2.50 (3H, s, COCH_3), 1.3 (3H, t) and (2H, q, J 10 Hz, COOCH_2 , CH_3), 7.26–8.19 (4H, m, disubstituted benzene), 13.9 (1H, s, NH hydrogen bonded). Similarly, other compounds (yields 50–58%) were prepared by coupling the appropriate sulfonamides with ethyl acetoacetate : **1b**, m.p. 200° ; **c**, 75° ; **d**, 156° ; **e**, 182° ; **f**, 190° .

1-Nitrophenyl-3-methyl-4-(4'-sulfonamoyl)pyrazolin-5-ones (2) : Compound **1** (0.01 mol) dissolved in acetic acid, was added to a solution of 4-nitrophenylhydrazine (0.01 mol) in minimum amount of acetic acid and refluxed for 5–6 h. The product, **2a** obtained after usual workup was crystallized from ethanol, (62%), m.p. 176° (Found : C, 47.70; H, 3.45; N, 20.5. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_6\text{O}_5\text{S}$ calcd. for : C, 47.76; H, 3.48; N, 20.8%); ν_{max} 3220 (NH), 1685 (CO), 1520 (NH-N=C), 1130 (SO_2) and 750 cm^{-1} (p -disubstituted phenyl); δ (CDCl_3) 2.5 (3H, s, CH_3), 7.26–8.30 (8H, m, substituted phenyl), 9.2 (2H, s, NH_2), 14.0 (1H, s, NH hydrogen bonded). Similarly other compounds (yields 50–60%) were prepared : **2b**, m.p. 139° ; **c**, 120° ; **d**, 105° ; **e**, 79° ; **f**, 103° .

References

1. A. A. ABOUOV, W. A. ABDULLA, and I. A. E. L. SAKKA, *J. Drug Res.*, 1975, 7, 1; I. M. ROUSHDI, I. A. E. SEBAL, and N. S. HABIB, *Egypt Pharm. Sci.*, 1975, 16, 407; N. B. DAS and A. S. MITTRA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, 16, 688; H. KONOTSURE and Z. KATSUCHIKO, Ger. Pat. 2639597/1977 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1978, 88, 206121); H. G. GARG and C. PRAKASH, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1971, 14, 175; W. RILTER, *Curr. Med. Res. Opin.*, 1977, 4, 564; K. HOWLAND, US Pat. 2458780/1949 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1950, 44, 5821).